

BUSINESS PROCESS REENGINEERING AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION OF LICENSED AND AUTHORIZED DEPOSIT TAKING SACCO SOCIETIES IN THE COAST REGION COUNTIES, KENYA

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Abstract: The deposit taking and credit cooperative societies have been in the process of significant transformation. The force behind this transformation of the deposit taking and credit cooperative societies is innovation in information technologies which has led to adoption of Business Process Reengineering projects by SACCOs. Guided by this background, the study examined the influence of business process reengineering on customer satisfaction of deposit taking and credit cooperative societies in coastal region counties, Kenya. The specific objectives were; Internet Banking, Mobile Banking, Electronic funds transfer and Automated teller machines and the ascertainment of how they affected customer satisfaction of deposit taking and credit cooperative societies in coastal region counties, Kenya. This study was guided by diffusion innovation theory, bank led theory and open school system theory. The study adopted descriptive research design. Primary data was collected through research questionnaire that was developed and sent to the various customers of deposit taking and credit cooperative societies in coastal region counties, Kenya. The positive correlation between mobile banking and customer satisfaction shown by a correlation figure 0.378 and regression coefficient of 0.135 showed that mobile banking improved customer satisfaction of SACCOs. The positive correlation between internet banking and customer satisfaction shown by a correlation figure 0.514 and regression coefficient of 0.083 showed that internet banking improved customer satisfaction of SACCOs. The positive correlation between electronic funds transfer and customer satisfaction shown by a correlation figure 0.577 and regression coefficient of 0.572 showed that electronic funds transfer improved customer satisfaction of SACCOs. The positive correlation between automated teller machine and customer satisfaction shown by a correlation figure 0.626 and regression coefficient of 0.058 showed that automated teller machine improved customer satisfaction of SACCOs. The study recommends that; SACCOs should take advantage of wide network coverage to reach the unbanked population and enhance their services hence customer satisfaction. Additionally, the study recommends that the application software platform should be as simple as possible and user-friendly which could be used by virtually everybody. The SACCOs should assure customers that transacting online is safer and private to encourage the SACCO customers to embrace online banking. SACCOs should team up with cybersecurity experts to proactively counter any imminent threats on online banking. The SACCOs should improve the interbank electronic fund transfer to encourage customers to use the service. Also, charges on EFT services should be competitive to enhance the SACCOs customer satisfaction. Finally, the SACCOs should install ATMs in all towns since it was established from the study that the benefits of installing ATM to the SACCOs were plenty. SACCOs should renegotiate with the regulating authority to expand the withdrawal amount limit since it affected customer satisfaction of the SACCOs negatively. The SACCOs should encourage customers to use ATMs by slapping the counter service fee.

Keywords: Business Process Reengineering, Internet Banking, Mobile Banking, Automated Teller Machines, Electronic fund Transfer, and performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Business sustainability and competitiveness around the world has been subjected to increasing pressure as a result of the globalization of the world's economy. Organizations have to reinvent their business policies, procedures, processes, and their market niche in an effort to ensure their relevancy and sustainability (Anand and Selvaraj, 2013). Organizations can ensure their sustainability through remaining profitable, as well as through gaining significant control of their markets in relation to the services and products they are offering on the market. As such, the threat of new entrants particularly with multinationals companies, are constantly forcing organizations to strategically reinvent themselves to deal with the raising global pressure to produce products and services that meet the global market ideals (Arbore and Busacca, 2009). Consequently, various organizations are pointing to customer satisfaction as an approach that helps to develop and differentiate their services from their rivals, and as a tool for the development of competitive advantage (Narteh & Kuada, 2014). The tremendous growth of SACCO in Kenya has played a key role in economic empowerment and poverty reduction. However, they encounter significant challenges in relation to their relatively small sizes, low resource base, technical incompetent boards who carry out operational functions, lowly qualified employees and scarce information processing systems (Owen 2007).

Customer satisfaction is vital in the banking industry, as an organization is not guaranteed of a chance to repeat the service especially if a customer flags the experience as being unsatisfactory (Munari, *et al.*, 2013). Narteh and Kuada (2014) contend that banks' ability to offer satisfactory customer services is limited to their organizations' policies, processes and standards for service quality. This can be attributed to the fact that service quality significantly contributes to the attainment of customer satisfaction. According to Terpstra *et al.*, (2014), every time the banking sector experiences favorable customer satisfaction, there is often underlying factors and fundamentals that enhance customers' experience. In contrast, Narteh and Kuada (2014) argue that there are various factors that enhance positive customer experiences. They argue that the Business process reengineering is the key factor that promotes customer satisfaction in banking industry.

Many terms and various names are used to describe business process reengineering (BPR) including; 'working smarter', or 'new industrial engineering' or 'core process redesign'. Entirely these terms carry the same model of understanding which involves the process of incorporating business process redesign and the use of information technology to support the reengineering work. The subject of BPR is an interesting one and comprises discovering the state and procedures currently functioning in a business, eliminating redundancy and improving efficiency by redesigning the business processes and implementation of process modifications for competitive advantage. Sherwood-Smith (2010) postulates that the aim of BPR includes the provision of processes that allow organizations to attain their goals by establishing new techniques of organizing people, task organization, and IT system redesign. This is achieved through the identification of key processes, the examination and evaluation of these processes and through redesigning for efficacy and gains.

The banking environment in contemporary times is increasingly competitive as customers have sophisticatedly grown in their dealings with banks, in that there is an increased demand in their expectations from the provided banking services, and the convenience of switching to alternative banks. Owing to the competition levels in the banking sector, customers' expectations of the banks minimum service delivery has significantly risen. Consequently, banks have implemented various approaches to enable them to meet their customers' satisfaction and expectations and maintain competitiveness on the market. The Business Process Reengineering modality is among the various modalities being used to guarantee that business processes of banks are transformed to meet value and demand. Besides, it is also meant to minimize the time spent by clienteles in accessing numerous services provided by the organization. Therefore, this improves the service quality levels and ensures increased customer satisfaction. This customer satisfaction that results from the reengineering of projects within the banking sector can be evaluated from the customer's perspective. In other words, when a customer's expectation is satisfied through the bank's reengineering project, the said customer is presumed to be satisfied. Nonetheless, if their expectation exceeds the delivered service resulting from bank's reengineering project, the customer would be presumed to be dissatisfied.

From the Kenyan perspective, the shifting dynamic of the banking sector, including other financial institutions, has obliged players at every level to take part in reengineering. This study covers the influence of business process reengineering on customer satisfaction of deposit taking, saving and credit cooperative societies in coastal region counties in Kenya. It is argued that there is a need to reengineer the operations and strategies of the SACCOs to allow the accommodation of changes that occur in the external and internal business environment wherein the SACCOs are operating in, including the

whole financial sector. These changes in the external and internal business environment have resulted in variations in business processes. Therefore, to survive and succeed in the global economy, such businesses need to react to key trends that are restructuring markets. Henceforth, the changing aspects of the principal forces at work necessitate a renewed insertion of business process reengineering in SACCOs to underwrite the diversification and management of growth horizons by influencing profitability and productivity (Stalk, 2010).

The idea of Business Process Reengineering broadly entails the implementation of change in business processes. Nonetheless, Balasubramanian (2010), argues that this change needs to be dramatic to business processes. The dramatic change should not be limited to marginal or incremental improvements in nature as it is necessary to find breakthroughs for the performance of the organization in terms of quality, cost, service as well as time compression. It should have the potential to improve the services provided by an organization to, in turn, improve the satisfaction levels of the customers. This enhancement of the customers satisfaction is the underlying reason for most of reengineering projects.

In addition, Khuzaimah (2011) states that change within an organization can range from desirable advances to massive disappointments. This can be attributed to the fact that change can result in the improvement of an organization's fortunes or can all together aggravate the issue if not completed properly. Ordinarily, the implemented changes may fail to accomplish breakthrough for the organizations (Shin & Jemella, 2012). Conversely, organizations that fulfill the reengineering goals have the potential of improving and achieving customer satisfaction. Business Process Reengineering provides an avenue through which changes are carried out in organizations.

There are numerous studies on business reengineering that have been carried out both on the local and international level. In particular BPR implementation has been widely covered by various studies such as that by Disii (2011), Laibon (2014), Hagos (2012), Doyle (2014), and Mutinda (2009). Disii (2011) focused on its implementation at the Kenya Ports Authority. Also, Laibon (2014) conducted a research on the influences that BPR has on workforce turnover at the KK Security Group of Companies. Hagos (2012) focused his study on the implementation of BPR and its influences within Ethiopia's Ministry of Health and the Gambella region. Doyle's (2014) study concentrated on BPR for the enhancement of South Africa's bank credit operations. Lastly, Mutinda (2009) conducted an investigation of the role of human resource factors in BPR implementation at the KCB Group. However, none of these studies looked at the outcome of BPR on performance of SACCOs such as saving, deposit taking and credit cooperative societies in coastal region counties, Kenya. The current research thus intends to fill this gap regarding effect of BPR on performance of deposit taking and credit cooperative societies in coastal region counties, Kenya. The study endeavoured to achieve the following objectives:

1. To examine the effect of mobile banking on customer satisfaction of deposit taking and credit cooperative societies in Coastal Region counties, Kenya.
2. To determine the effect of internet banking on customer satisfaction of deposit taking and credit cooperative societies in Coastal Region counties, Kenya.
3. To establish the effect of electronic funds transfer on customer satisfaction of deposit taking and credit cooperative societies in Coastal Region counties, Kenya.
4. To evaluate the effect of automated teller machines on customer satisfaction of deposit taking and credit cooperative societies in Coastal Region counties Kenya.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Diffusion of Innovation Theory

The current world is enjoying great transformation and acceleration resulting from the remarkable development of information and technology, including the constant growth of the volume of information that has resulted in the advent of new types of activities and transactions in different fields (Joseph *et al.*, 2005). The SACCOs have been among the top sectors that have embraced numerous electronic applications to attain a competitive advantage strategy and promote its growth. Concerning the extensive application of information and communication technologies, SACCOs have availed new applications and systems that maximize the adoption of modern technology.

This theory is concerned with explaining "why, how and at what rate" novel technology and new ideas are carried through cultures. In conformity, Rogers (2003), claimed that diffusion involves the process through which innovations are communicated through specified channels over some time among the members of a social system. The diffusion of

innovation theory has varied origins, which span numerous disciplines. It has four main elements, including, innovations, time, communications channels, and the social system. Innovation entails the application of improved solutions that are align with new requirements, in existing market needs or articulated needs. This is attained through more effective services, products, technologies, processes or ideas, which are readily available to society, market, and government (Boston Consulting Group, 2009).

Diffusion represents a distinct form of communication, whereby the messages are centered on a new idea. Such newness of the idea contained in the message being communicated earns diffusion its distinctive appeal. Rogers (2003) postulates that it is the apparent newness of innovations together with the uncertainty linked to the newness that form the distinctive characteristic of innovation decision making. The diffusion of innovation theory is connected to the current theory as it demonstrates the process of newness and the implementation of BPR in the SACCO industry. BPR is one of the innovative approaches through which SACCOs can promote growth through radical redesign and coming up with new techniques.

Therefore, it is necessary for SACCOs to transform for traditional ways of offering services and adopt the current technology that would enable them to reduce cost, rise efficiency and meet customer expectations. In this study, diffusion innovation theory was used to show how the SACCOs industry in Kenya had adopted technology to remain competitive in the market and to meet their customers' expectations.

2.2 Bank Led Theory

The Bank Led Theory consists of a system of three key entities, namely, the bank, the customer, and the retail agent. This system's operation begins from the SACCO, which develops their financial services and products that are then delivered to the customers the retail agents, who interact directly with customers on behalf of the SACCOs. Principally, the SACCOs role mainly concerns cash in and cash out transactions (opening and holding accounts). Whereas the retail agent's role entails the verification of client's ID, processing applications, carrying out face-to-face transactions, creating groups, vending insurance products, distributing small values to the SACCO, handling small remittances, and collecting small deposits, and loans (Chowdhury, 2010).

Clients are allowed to access the assortment of non-financial and financial services available. The retail agent facilitates the communication between customers and the SACCO. In turn, the SACCO holds the responsibility of installing electronic technology like POS devices or mobile phones for retail agents. However, there are exceptions such as in Brazil, where the bank authorizes management companies to fulfill responsibilities on its behalf. Such delegated responsibilities include the equipping of the retail agent with technology and observing their performances, though the bank's accountability to the customers still holds in case of the retail agent's negligence or fraud. (Lyman *et al.*, 2006).

Apart from Brazil, this model has also been applied in South Africa, Pakistan and India. In India, the branchless regulating policy requires the retail agent to disclose every transaction on the bank's books (RBI circular, 2006). This model has been recognized as the facilitator of the interaction between the financial institutions and the customers residing in distant places and who can enjoy non-financial services and financial services by going to the retail agents. The common risk linked to the bank led theory may chiefly be associated with the zero training of the retail agent employees, and the definite security of the sequence, which is closely related to the risk linked to the conventional branch-based banking.

2.3 The Open School System Theory

Organizations are made up of interconnected units or subsystems (Lawrence, Lorsch & Thompson, 2011). Therefore, change in a single unit has an effect on other parts of the organization leading to a change in the organization's overall performance. According to

Lawrence, Lorsch and Thompson (2011), organizations that function in environments that are stable and predictable can achieve increased productivity and efficiency when their organization follows a traditional hierarchical structure. In contrast, organizations that function in environments characterized with fast changing markets and technologies, tend to be increasingly successful, particularly if they adopt technology in their operations.

Lawrence, Lorsch and Thompson (2011) further argue that an increase in the rate of changes in an organizations external environment warrants for the specialization of its subsystems' functions. In other words, organizations need to embrace newer and improved technologies while pushing for co-operation between its various teams of personnel. Technology, which act as inputs for an organization, are transformed to produce outputs that improve efficiency and are released into

the changing environment (Sarah and Toman, 2005). The underlying argument of this theory is that information technology significantly influences organizational performance and thus encourages more changes for the attainment of customer requirements.

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

A typical conceptual framework comprises of both the independent variables and the dependent variable with the independent variables causing the changes in the dependent variable. The researcher's goal was to create an understanding of the dependent variable (Kothari, 2004). The conceptual framework in this study involved independent variables: mobile banking, electronic funds transfer, internet banking, and Automatic teller machine. The dependent variable in this study was customer satisfaction.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Mobile Banking and Customer satisfaction

The perceived low demand levels, low SACCO income levels, high SACCO fees, lack of personalized services and products and narrow geographical coverage guaranteed that only a minor percentage of the Kenyan population has access to SACCO services. The operations of SACCOs are financed by the income earned from fees, which are generated from the services offered, the interests earned from deposits and the interests earned from offered loans. The shift in banking operations, for instance from the traditional banking services to the agency banking and eventually to mobile banking has yielded increased benefits for SACCOs and their customers. These benefits are mainly as a result of reduced operating costs of the SACCOs and the convenience and affordability of their services and products mobile transactions yield reduced fees (Keagan *et al.*, 2015). Mobile banking encompasses the provision of SACCO services, most importantly with the use of mobile devices. Its emergence was promoted by competition advanced by the telecommunication industry, for instance M-pesa services offered by Safaricom and Airtel Money offered by the former's competitor, Airtel. These mobile banking services facilitate the depositing of money into customers' accounts, as well as the transfer of funds to other users such as traders, relatives and friends; resulting in increased convenience (Khrawish, 2016).

The SACCO sector is thus forced to embrace technological change to sustain their competitiveness. To achieve competitive advantage in the technological finance service industry, SACCOs are expected to acknowledge the value of differentiating themselves from other financial institutions by continuously innovating their service distribution channels (Daniels, 2015).

The bureaucratic process involved in the opening of accounts in banks sidelined most of the rural poor who could not meet the qualifications of owning accounts. SACCOs have to streamline such processes and innovate new approaches of doing so. A good proportion of banks have been innovative with their M-banking products, namely, Family bank's Pesa Pap, Equity bank's M-kesho, KCBs Mobibank and the Commercial Bank of Africa's M-shwari. SACCOs can also adopt this M-banking mode and satisfy the customers. Mobile banking services yields various advantages for the banks and their customers. Notably, it negates the geographical restrictions to customers and as a result increases convenience. Also, it gets rid of the time limitations of customers receiving banking services as banks can operate from any place and throughout the day via the mobile devices. Besides, mobile banking improves the security of funds and efficiency of cash management.

Mobile banking's effectiveness, especially to customers' satisfaction has ignited substantial arguments within the literature realm. As a result, existing literature hold contradicting opinions on the connection between customer satisfaction and mobile banking. A portion of the literature holds the view that mobile banking services are significant contributors to customer satisfaction (Ngilangwa & Venkatakrishnan, 2014). Conversely, the opposing portion of literature maintains that there is no relation between the two factors (Kalimang'asi *et al.*, 2014). All in all, the common view between these two opposing portions is that mobile banking offers speedy, reliable, convenient and friendly services. With such attributes in mind, it is hard to completely discredit the link between customer satisfaction and mobile banking.

Internet Banking and Customer satisfaction

Internet banking is among the major developments that has occurred in the SACCO sector. This banking feature allows the SACCOs clients to access their traditional banking accounts through the internet. Such ability to access accounts virtually allows the customers to carry out their desired transactions within the rigorous security checks put in place (Essinger, 1999). According to the American Office of Controller of Currency (2001) internet banking could be understood as the process of using the internet to avail normal banking services.

The adoption of internet banking offers an increased level of flexibility and convenience to the SACCOs customers. Such benefits can be attributed the high levels of control that the customers have over their banking accounts. Various scholars have investigated the opinions held by customers over internet banking services. The most notable investigation was conducted by El Shebini *et al* (2007) who sought to study the application of internet banking, its related problems as well as the various challenges customers were faced with while using these services. The researcher's scope was limited to Kuwait and it arrived at the conclusion that the country's internet banking activities had led to the improvement of five key services, such as open accounts, review account balance, pay bills, transfer funds between own accounts, and obtained detailed transactions histories.

Electronic Funds Transfer and Customer satisfaction

Electronic Funds Transfer entails the transferring of funds electronically between bank accounts, either within one SACCO or across several institutions, through computer-based systems and without the direct intervention of SACCO employees. Electronic funds transfer (EFT) is among the best money management tools at the disposal of businesses. As opposed to using traditional methods such as cheques, EFTs allow for businesses and their clients to exchange funds electronically. They are also termed as Automated Clearing House (ACH) transactions, which denotes the countrywide electronic payment network through which the authentic clearing of all electronic payments, including payment-related information between the financial institutions is conducted. It is possible to send payment-related information alongside ACH transactions in a process referred to as Electronic Data Interchange. Kariuki (2014) points out that even though the ACH is not a common term, great familiarity can be derived from the different types of electronic payments, which can be opened through ACH networks.

E-banking has various effects on customer satisfaction under the SACCO sector. Grunroos (2008), argues that there exists not only a solid but a positive connection between the E-service quality and customers' satisfaction. Likewise, Parasuraman *et al.*, (2008) also contends that there is a very substantial and durable relationship between the aforementioned factors. Taking a different approach, Jain and Gupta (2004) modified the relationship in a simplified formula and concluded that pronounced customer satisfaction is immensely dependent on the customers' receipt of improved and quality of service.

Various other studies have also pointed out to a connection between E-banking services and customers' satisfaction levels. For instance, the study by Asiyanbi and Ishola (2018) supported the idea that the customer satisfaction levels in the SACCO sector rises during the application of E-Banking services. On the same note, a different study by Ranaweera and Neely,

(2003) documented that the E-service quality is the initial step towards customer satisfaction. Bei and Chiao's (2006) study in the banking sector revealed a major association between service quality and degrees of customer satisfaction. To finish with, Zhou (2004) postulated that E-banking services quality in relation to reliability has a substantial influence on the customer satisfaction levels.

Automated Teller Machine and Customer satisfaction

Automated teller machines, commonly known as ATMs, are electronic devices that facilitate the debiting and crediting of banking accounts, without necessarily having clients to queue in banking halls. In agreement Rose (2000) stated that an ATM encompasses an arrangement of a computer terminal, a cash vault, and a record keeping system, embodied in a single unit that allows clients to access banking book keeping systems via a plastic card that contains a PIN or by entering a distinct code number into computer terminals connected to banking computerized records throughout the day. Customers using an ATM card are able to access banks systems and in turn access multiple forms of retail bank systems. Therefore, customers enjoy unlimited access of banking services. According to the Federal Trade Council (1996), ATMs are typically electronic terminals, which facilitate customers to use banking services anytime they desire. SACCOs have developed strategic approaches for their ATM machine's locations to enhance customers' access. Typically, these machines are set up outside banking halls including airports, shopping malls and locations where banks consider as less practical to set up branches. The importance of such an approach is to expand access and coverage to the various customers that the sector serves.

Originally, ATMs were introduced to enable customers to withdraw funds from their accounts. Nonetheless, with technological advancements, modifications were instituted to allow them to deposit funds through the ATMs and make online transfers between their accounts without having to physically access banking halls. The integration between ATMs and human tellers improves the SACCOs' productivity and efficiency. It also cuts down on the time required by customers to access SACCOs' services, thereby improving their satisfaction levels. Particularly, the SACCOs productivity when using ATMs is higher than the use of human tellers. In this sense, Rose (2000) documented that ATMs complete averagely 6400 transactions annually as compared to human tellers who amount to 6300 transactions. Such variation is attributed to attributes of ATMs being able to provide round-the-clock services as opposed to the human tellers.

4. RESEARCH DESIGN

The study at hand used a descriptive research design. Descriptive surveys allow researchers to apply both quantitative and qualitative data in an objective fashion without modifying the study environment (Mugenda *et al.*, 2008). In support Saunders *et al.*, (2009) states that during the collection of data, researchers need to maintain objectivity and should interpret the data and the information as obtained. To counter the possibilities of study biases, researchers should not introduce their opinions into the respective studies. With this understanding, the descriptive survey study design was suitable for the current study as it facilitated research objectivity and allowed for the summarization of data using inferential and descriptive statistics; which in turn simplified the understanding of the study's findings.

5. DESCRIPTIVE RESULTS

Descriptive statistics are used to describe the basic features of the data in study, giving simple summaries about the sample and the measures.

5.1 Mobile banking

The researcher wanted to evaluate various views and perceptions of the respondents in respect to the effect of mobile banking services on customer satisfaction as part of business process reengineering at SACCOs.

From the table 1 shown below, the results indicates that most respondents agreed that adoption of mobile banking services by SACCOs affects customer satisfaction. This is depicted by a mean score of 4.7333 and a standard deviation of .62031. Majority of the respondents agreed that ease of use of mobile phones application software positively affects customer satisfaction in SACCOs. This is indicated by a mean score of 4.7200 and standard deviation of .62520. As to whether mobile phones cost has inverse relationship with customer satisfaction of SACCOs, majority of the respondents agreed with the findings as indicated with a mean of 4.6533 and a standard deviation of .68529 that indeed mobile phones cost have inverse relationship with customer satisfaction of SACCOs.

The respondents were asked if the customers were reluctant in embracing mobile banking services and most of them disagreed with this statement with a mean score of 1.7200 and a standard deviation of .71532.

Table 1: Mobile Banking

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Adoption of mobile banking by SACCOs affects Customer satisfaction	150	2.00	5.00	4.7333	.62031
Ease of use of mobile phones application software positively affects customer satisfaction in SACCOs	150	2.00	5.00	4.7200	.62520
Mobile phones cost has inverse relationship with customer satisfaction of SACCOs	150	2.00	5.00	4.6533	.68529
Customers are reluctant in embracing mobile banking	150	1.00	4.00	1.7200	.71532
Valid N (listwise)	150				

The findings of the study have been supported by the findings of Coetzee, Kamau and Njema (2013) that stated that the main benefits of M-banking are affordable, fast and secure transactions. M-banking access amongst previously unbanked groups is believed to have a direct, positive on users, since it has brought about a transaction from informal to formal transactions and hence alleviated poverty and caused economic development (Coetzee *et al.*, 2013).

5.2 Internet Banking

The researcher wanted to evaluate various views and perceptions of the respondents in respect to the effect of internet banking services on customer satisfaction as part of business process reengineering at SACCOs. The result is presented below.

Table 2: Internet Banking

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Customer prefer over the counter transactions than online banking	150	1.00	4.00	1.9000	.82535
Cybercrime has negatively affected uptake of internet banking	150	2.00	5.00	4.5267	.71133
Extent of internet coverage influences internet banking	150	2.00	5.00	4.5200	.69243
Age is a significant factor in Internet banking	150	1.00	4.00	1.7000	.68297
Valid N (listwise)	150				

The findings of the study are in agreement with the findings of many studies showings that electronic banking applications is diminishing operational cost and increasing profitability and performance in banks (Osborne, 2013; Mallick, 2015). Benefits of internet banking are cost saving, reaching new segments of the population, efficiency, enhancement of the bank's reputation and better customer service and satisfaction, the online banking strengthens the relationship between the service provider (e.g., SACCOs) and the customer. The main goal of every organization is to maximize profits for its owners and banks are not any exception. Automated e-banking services offer a perfect opportunity for maximizing profits (Kihumba, 2014). Therefore, internet banking affect customer satisfaction in a positive manner.

5.3 Electronic Funds Transfer

The researcher wanted to evaluate various views and perceptions of the respondents in respect to the effect of electronic funds transfer services on customer satisfaction as part of business process reengineering at SACCOs. The result is presented below.

Table 3: Electronic Funds Transfer

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Customers are reluctant in embracing EFT due to security reasons	150	2.00	5.00	4.0333	.95127
Uptake of EFT services by customers are affected by level of illiteracy	150	2.00	5.00	4.3733	.79888
Frequent electricity outage is disturbing my ability to use services of the SACCOs	150	2.00	5.00	4.2933	.84779
Valid N (listwise)	150				

From the study findings, majority of the respondents agreed that majority of the customers are reluctant in embracing EFT due to security reasons with a mean of 4.0333. Also, many of the respondents agreed that that uptake of EFT services by customers are affected by level of illiteracy as indicated by a mean of 4.3733. However, majority of respondents (4.2933) agreed that frequent electricity outage affects the ability to use EFT services as indicated by a mean of 4.2933.

The findings of the study are in agreement with the findings of Kariuki (2014) that stated that Electronic Funds Transfer (EFT) is the electronic transfer of money from one SACCO account to another, either within a single financial institution or across multiple institutions, via computer-based systems, without direct intervention of bank staff. As the name implies, EFTs enable banks and their customers hence improving service delivery by SACCOs to their customers.

5.4 Automated Teller Machine

The researcher wanted to evaluate various views and perceptions of the respondents in respect to the effect of automated teller machine services on customer satisfaction as part of business process reengineering at SACCOs. The result is presented below.

Table 4: Automated Teller Machine

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Benefits of installing ATM to the SACCOs are plenty than the cost of installing ATM	150	2.00	5.00	4.5000	.80059
ATM amount withdrawal limit negatively affects customer satisfaction in SACCOs	150	2.00	5.00	4.6467	.66692
Customers prefer ATM banking than hall banking	150	3.00	5.00	4.6667	.59828
Additional security requirements due to ATM installation affects its use by customers	150	1.00	4.00	2.0267	.80223
Valid N (listwise)	150				

From the study findings, the majority respondents were in agreement that benefits of installing ATM to the SACCOs are plenty than the cost of installing them by a mean score of 4.5000. Also, majority of the respondents were in agreement that ATM amount withdrawal limit negatively affects customer satisfaction and customers prefer ATM banking than hall banking with a mean of 4.6467 and 4.6667 respectively. On whether additional security requirements due to ATM installation affect its use by customers, the respondents had a varying view as indicated by a mean of 2.0267. This is in agreement with study by Ongare (2013) who did a study on the effect of electronic banking on customer satisfaction of SACCOs.

5.5 Customer Satisfaction

The researcher wanted to evaluate various views and perceptions of the respondents in respect to customer satisfaction SACCOs. The results are presented in table 5 below.

Table 5: Customer Satisfaction

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Mobile banking services has enhanced customer satisfaction at SACCOs	150	2.00	5.00	4.3867	.84969
Internet banking services have facilitated customer satisfaction at SACCOs	150	2.00	5.00	4.5200	.72092
Electronic funds transfer services at SACCOs have enhanced customer satisfaction	150	2.00	5.00	4.3200	.86171
ATM services have enhanced customer satisfaction of SACCOs	150	2.00	5.00	4.1933	.96026
Valid N (listwise)	150				

From the table 5 shown above, the results indicates that most respondents agreed that Mobile banking services has enhanced customer satisfaction at SACCOs. This is depicted by a mean score of 4.3867 and a standard deviation of .84969. Majority of the respondents agreed that Internet banking services have facilitated customer satisfaction at SACCOs. This is indicated by a mean score of 4.5200 and standard deviation of .72092. As to whether electronic funds transfer services at SACCOs have enhanced customer satisfaction, majority of the respondents agreed with the findings as indicated with a mean of 4.3200 and a standard deviation of .86171 that indeed electronic funds transfer have enhanced customer satisfaction at SACCOs.

The respondents were asked if ATM services have enhanced customer satisfaction at SACCOs and most of them agreed with this statement with a mean score of 4.1933 and a standard deviation of .96026.

6. CORRELATION RESULTS

The study conducted correlation analysis to test strength of association/relationship between the research variables. Correlation is the measure of the relationship or association between two continuous numeric variables. Correlation indicates both direction and degree to which they correlate with one another from case to case without implying that one is causing the other. Correlation results give a correlation coefficient which measures the linear association between two variables (Crossman, 2013).

The value of correlation coefficient ranges between -1 and +1. A correlation coefficient of +1 indicates that two variables are perfectly related in positive linear. A correlation of -1 indicates that two variables are negatively linearly related and a correlation coefficient of 0 indicates that there is no linear relationship between two variables.

Table 6: Pearson Correlation Matrix

		Customer Satisfaction	Mobile banking	Internet banking	Electronic funds transfer	Automated teller machine
Customer Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)					
Mobile banking	Pearson Correlation	.378	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.006	.000			
Internet banking	Pearson Correlation	.514**	.761**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.003	.000		
Electronic funds transfer	Pearson Correlation	.577	.706	.636	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.007	.000	.000	.000	
Automated teller machine	Pearson Correlation	.626	.522	.629	.562	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

The results of the correlation analysis revealed a clear positive correlation between the independent variables; mobile banking, internet banking, electronic funds transfer and automated teller machine and dependent variable customer satisfaction. The analysis indicates the coefficient of correlation 'r' equal to 0.378, 0.514, 0.577 and 0.626 for mobile banking, internet banking, electronic funds transfer and automated teller machine and dependent respectively. The analysis revealed a positive relationship between independent variables and dependent variable.

7. REGRESSION RESULTS

The regression analysis was done using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method. However, before running the regressions, descriptive statistics and correlation analysis were considered. Regression results showed the relationships between the different variables considered in the study.

7.1 Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Table 7: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.722 ^a	.520	.512	.26253

a. Predictors: (Constant), Mobile Banking, Internet Banking, Electronic Funds Transfer, Automated Teller Machine.

The model explained 52% of the variance (Adjusted R Square = 0.512) on customer satisfaction. Clearly, there are factors other than the four proposed in this model which could be used to predict customer satisfaction. However, this was still a good model as Gaur and Guar (2013) pointed out that as much as lower value R square 0.10 – 0.20 was acceptable in social science research.

This meant that 52% of the relationship was explained by the identified four factors namely mobile banking, internet banking, electronic funds transfer and automated teller machine. The remaining 48% was explained by other factors not studied in this research. In summary, the four factors studied namely, mobile banking, internet banking, electronic funds transfer and automated teller machine determined 52% of the relationship while the rest 48% was explained or determined by other factors.

7.2 Analysis of Variance

Table 8: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	16.361	3	4.090	60.416	.000 ^b
	Residual	15.098	146	.068		
	Total	31.459	149			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Mobile Banking, Internet Banking, Electronic Funds Transfer, Automated Teller Machine.

This study used ANOVA to establish the significance of the regression model. Statistical significance was considered significant if the p-value was less or equal to 0.05. The significance of the regression model had a p-value of 0.00 which is less than 0.05. This indicated that the regression model was statistically significant in predicting the effect of BPR on customer satisfaction at SACCOs.

The ANOVA results indicated that the model was significant at $F = 60.416$, and a df of 3 with $p < .05$. At 95% confidence level, the analysis indicated a high reliability of the results obtained thus indicating that the study was statistically determined. These results agreed with other results (Bowman, 2013).

7.3 Multiple Regression Results

Multiple regression analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable. The results are as follows:

Table 9: Regression Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.633	.257		2.4655	.014
	Mobile Banking	.135	.081	.113	1.676	.005
	Internet Banking	.083	.088	.079	.950	.343
	Electronic Funds Transfer	.572	.059	.586	9.678	.000
	Automated Teller Machine	.058	.071	.061	.831	.417

The regression equation was;

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \epsilon.$$

Where Y = Customer Satisfaction (dependent variable)

β_0 = Constant of Regression

$\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = The Beta coefficients for the corresponding X (independent) terms, representing the net effect the variable had on the dependent variable, as Xs in the question remain constant.

X_1 = Mobile Banking

X_2 = Internet Banking

X_3 = Electronic Funds Transfer

X_4 = Automated Teller Machine

ϵ = Error term

Therefore, the regression equation: $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \epsilon.$

$$Y = 0.633 + 0.135X_1 + 0.572X_3 + \epsilon.$$

This also indicated that taking all factors constant at zero, customer satisfaction was at a value of $\beta_0 = 2.633$. The findings showed that taking all independent variable at zero, a unit increase as a result of mobile banking gave a value of 0.135 increase in customer satisfaction. It also indicated that a unit increase as a result of internet banking led to a value of 0.083 increase on customer satisfaction. A unit increase on electronic funds transfer gave a value of 0.572 increase on customer satisfaction. The study also showed that a unit increase of automated teller machine gave a value of 0.058 on customer satisfaction at SACCOs. The study showed that only two variables had positive and significant relationship with customer satisfaction, the most influential being electronic funds transfer which had regression coefficient of 0.572 and a p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.005 then followed by mobile banking which had regression coefficient of 0.135 and a p-value of 0.005. However, there was no significant relationship between internet banking and customer satisfaction (0.343), automated teller machine and customer satisfaction (0.417). The findings of the study were consistent with the findings of other scholars. Gudmundsson *et al.*, (2013) concludes that electronic funds transfer positively affects customer satisfaction of SACCOs.

8. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

8.1 Effect of mobile banking on customer satisfaction

From the study findings, the respondents agreed that mobile network coverage nationally affects operational cost of the SACCOs. Also, many respondents agreed that ease use of mobile phones application software positively affect customer satisfaction of the SACCOs and that mobile phones cost have inverse relationship with customer satisfaction of SACCOs. Majority of the respondents however, disagreed that customers are reluctant in embracing mobile banking. The positive correlation between mobile banking and customer satisfaction shown by a correlation figure 0.378 and regression coefficient of 0.135 showed that mobile banking improved customer satisfaction of SACCOs. These findings agreed with a study by Kigen (2013) who studied impact of mobile banking on transaction cost of microfinance institutions and found out that by then, mobile banking had reduced transaction cost considerably and also reduced long queues of customers in those microfinance institutions.

8.2 Effect of internet banking on customer satisfaction

On the effect of internet banking, the study findings established that many customers prefer over the counter transactions than online banking. Also, many respondents agreed that cybercrime had negatively affected uptake of internet banking and extent of internet coverage which influences internet banking. Majority of the respondents disagreed that age is a significant factor in internet banking uptake. The positive correlation between internet banking and customer satisfaction shown by a correlation figure 0.514 and regression coefficient of 0.083 showed that internet banking improved customer satisfaction of SACCOs. These findings agreed with a study by Mahotra and Singh (2014) who examined the impact of internet banking on banks' performance and risk in India. The study examined a comprehensive set of 10 measures of financial performance that made it possible for the authors to look into bank performance critically. By developing a deeper understanding of these phenomena, the researchers drew more insightful inferences about the impact of internet banking on business strategies, production process and customer satisfaction. The result of the study revealed that on average, Internet SACCOs are more profitable than non-internet SACCOs and are operating at lower cost hence satisfying customer needs.

8.3 Effect of electronic funds transfer on customer satisfaction

From the study findings, the majority of respondents agreed that customers were reluctant in embracing EFT due to security reasons. Also, many respondents agreed that uptake of EFT services by customers was affected by the level of illiteracy and EFT affects the customer satisfaction of SACCOs. The positive correlation between electronic funds transfer and customer satisfaction shown by a correlation figure 0.577 and regression coefficient of 0.572 showed that electronic funds transfer improved customer satisfaction of SACCOs.

8.4 Effect of automated teller machine on customer satisfaction

From the study findings, the majority of the respondents agreed that benefits of installing ATM to the SACCOs are plenty than the cost of installing ATM. Also, many respondents agreed that ATM amount withdrawal limit negatively affected the customer satisfaction and customers prefer ATM banking than hall banking thus affecting customer satisfaction of the SACCOs. Majority of the respondents disagreed that additional security requirements due to ATM installation affect customer satisfaction of the SACCOs. The positive correlation between automated teller machine and customer satisfaction shown by a correlation figure 0.626 and regression coefficient of 0.058 showed that automated teller machine improved customer satisfaction of SACCOs. This is in agreement with study by Ongare (2013), who did the study on the effect of electronic banking on customer satisfaction of commercial banks in Kenya. The study sought to establish whether there exists a relationship between the dependent variables, for example, customer satisfaction measured by customer loyalty and retention and the independent variables consisting of number of ATMs, number of debits and credits cards issued to customers, number of point-of-sale terminals and usage levels of mobile banking, internet banking and electronic funds transfer, as companies of e-banking. The study used secondary data which was collected from the annual report of commercial banks and central banks of Kenya. The study used both descriptive and inferential statistics in analyzing the data. The findings of the study were that e-banking had a strong and significant effect on profitability and service delivery on customers. Thus, there exists a positive relationship between e-banking and customer satisfaction. The significance test showed that the influence of bank innovations on customer satisfaction was statistically significant.

9. CONCLUSION

The conclusions were made based on the research objectives as follows;

9.1 Effect of mobile banking on customer satisfaction

From the findings, it is concluded that mobile network coverage affects service delivery of SACCOs hence customer satisfaction. Also, the ease of use of mobile phones application software positively affects customer satisfaction of the SACCOs, and mobile phones cost has inverse relationship with customer relationship of SACCOs. However, the study concludes that customers are not reluctant in embracing mobile banking.

9.2 Effect of internet banking on customer satisfaction

The study found customers prefer over the counter transactions than online banking. Also, cybercrime has negatively affected uptake of internet banking and extent of internet coverage which influences internet banking. Besides, the age of an individual is not a significant factor in internet uptake in SACCOs.

9.3 Effect of electronic funds transfer on customer satisfaction

On the effect of electronic funds transfer, the study concludes that SACCO customers are reluctant in embracing EFT due to security reasons. Also, the uptake of EFT services by SACCO customers is affected by the level of illiteracy and EFT affects customer satisfaction.

9.4 Effect of automated teller machine on customer satisfaction

The study concludes that benefits of installing ATM to the SACCO are plenty than the cost of installing ATM. Also, ATM amount withdrawal limit negatively affects customer satisfaction and SACCO customers prefer ATM banking than hall banking thus affecting customer satisfaction of the SACCO. However, it was not established whether additional security requirements due to ATM installation affect customer satisfaction of SACCO.

10. RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommends that; SACCOs should take advantage of wide network coverage to reach the unbanked population and enhance their services hence customer satisfaction. Additionally, the study recommends that the application software platform should be as simple as possible and user-friendly which could be used by virtually everybody. Secondly, the SACCOs should assure customers that transacting online is safer and private to encourage the SACCO customers to embrace online banking. Also, SACCOs should team up with cybersecurity experts to proactively counter any imminent threats on online banking. Thirdly, the SACCOs should improve the interbank electronic fund transfer to encourage customers to use the service. Also, charges on EFT services should be competitive to enhance the SACCOs customer satisfaction. Finally, the SACCOs should install ATMs in all towns since it was established from the study that the benefits of installing ATM to the SACCOs are plenty. Also, SACCOs should renegotiate with the regulating authority to expand the withdrawal amount limit since it affected customer satisfaction of the SACCOs negatively. The SACCOs should encourage customers to use ATMs by slapping the counter service fee.

10.1 Recommendations for Further Research

The study was done on deposit taking SACCOs. This research should be replicated to other non-deposit taking SACCOs and results be compared so as to establish whether there is consistency among different SACCOs in Kenya on the effect of business reengineering on customer satisfaction.

REFERENCES

- [1] Anand, S. V., & Selvaraj, M. (2013). Evaluation of Service Quality and its Impact on Customer Satisfaction in Indian Banking Sector: A Comparative study using SERVPERF. *Life Science Journal*, PP.3267-3274.
- [2] Anyasi, F. I., & Otubu, P. A. (2009). Mobile Phone Technology in Banking System: Its Economic Effect. *Reserch Journal of Informtion Technology 1(1)*, 1-5.
- [3] Arbore, A., & Busacca, B. (2009). Customer Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction in Retail Banking: Exploring the Asymmetric Impact of Attribute Performances. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, PP. 271-280.
- [4] Aremu, M. A., & Saka, H. T. (2014). The impact of information technology on library management: a marketing perspective. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (Oman Chapter)*, 4(4), p.1.
- [5] Asiyambi, H., & Ishola, A. (2018). E-Banking services impact and customer satisfaction in selected bank branches in Ibadan metropolis, Oyo state, Nigeria. *Accounting*, 4(4), PP. 153-160.
- [6] Balasubramanian, S. (2010). *Successful reengineering implementation strategy*.
- [7] Bryman, A., & Bell, E. (2015). *Business Research Methods*. London: Oxford University Press.
- [8] Circuar, R. (2006). *Reserve Bank of India*.
- [9] Cox, J. W., & Hassard, J. (2005). Triangulation in organizational research representation of Organizational Science. *Management Science*, 12, PP. 109-133.
- [10] Davenport, T. H., & Short, J. E. (2009). *The new industrial engineering: information technology and business process redesign*.

- [11] Disii, F. (2011). *Implementation of BPR and benchmarking at Kenya Ports Authority*. University of Nairobi: School of Business.
- [12] Doyle, M. (2014). *Business Process Re-engineering for the Improvement of Bank Credit Operations*. The University of Johannesburg.
- [13] Epetimehin, F. M., & Ekundayo, O. (2011). Organizational knowledge management: Survival strategy for Nigeria insurance industry. *Interdisciplinary Review of Economics and Management*, PP. 9-15.
- [14] Evans, J. R., & Berman, B. (2009). *Marketing, 4 edition*. London: Collier MacMillan Publishers.
- [15] Fraenkel, J. R., & Wallen, N. E. (2011). *How to Design and Evaluate Research in Education*. New York: McGraw-Hill Higher Education.
- [16] Graham, R. S. (2010). *Business process reengineering: strategies for occupational health and safety*.
- [17] Grönroos, C. (2008). Marketing services: The case of a missing product. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 13, pp. 322-338.
- [18] Group, B. C. (2009). *BCG Innovation*.
- [19] Habib, M., & Wazir, J. (2012). *Reengineering the Corporations*. London: MacMillan Publishers.
- [20] Hagos, S. (2012). *Assessment of business process reengineering implementation and result within Ethiopian ministry of health and Gambelle regional health bureau context*. Blekinge Institute of Technology.
- [21] Hammer, M. (2009). Reengineering Work: Don't automate, elaborate. *Harvard Business Review*, July-August, PP. 104-112.
- [22] Jack, W., & Suri, T. (2010). The Economics of M-PESA. *Unpublished paper on M-PESA Georgetown University*.
- [23] Janson, R. (2010). How Reengineering Transforms Organizations to Satisfy Customers. *National Productivity Review*, p. 45.
- [24] Kalimang'asi, N., Bundala, D. M., & Mlowosa, T. P. (2014). Measuring Contributions of Information Technology on Bank's Service Offering: The Case of National Microfinance Bank (NMB) Ltd Tanzania. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, Volume 4, Issue 11, November 2014 1 ISSN 2250- 3153.
- [25] Khuzaimah, A. L. (2011). *The impact of business process reengineering on organizational Performance*. (Doctoral dissertation, Universiti Utara Malaysia).
- [26] Laibon, P. (2014). *The Effect of Business process reengineering on staff turnover: A case study of KK Security Group of Companies*. United States International University-Kenya.
- [27] Lotfollah, N., Ziaul, H., Seyed, M. N., & Saeedreza, H. (2012). Impact of IT on process improvement. *Journal of emerging trends in computing and information sciences*. 3,(1).
- [28] Lyman, M., Timothy, A., Ivatury, G., & Stefan, S. (2006). *Use of Agents in Branchless Banking for the Poor; Rewards, Risks and Regulations*. Washington D.C.
- [29] Marjanovic, O. (2008). Supporting the "soft" side of business process reengineering. *Business Process Management Journal*, 6(1), pp.43-55.
- [30] Mugenda, O., & Mugenda, A. (2008). *Research Methods : Quantitative and Qualitative approaches*. Nairobi: ACT Press.
- [31] Munari, L., Ielasi, F., & Bajetta, L. (2013). Customer Satisfaction Management in Italian Banks. *Qualitative Research in Financial Markets*, pp. 139-160.
- [32] Mutinda, M. (2009). *Assessment of HR factors in implementation of business process reengineering at KCB*. (Unpublished MBA project). School of Business: University of Nairobi.
- [33] Narteh, B., & Kuada, J. (2014). Customer Satisfaction with Retail Banking Services in Ghana. *Thunderbird International Business Review*, pp. 353-371.

- [34] Ngilangwa, E., & Venkatakrishnan, V. (2014). Customer Satisfaction On Mobile-Phone Money Transfer Services* Usage In Dodoma Urban, Tanzania. Volume No. 4 (2014), Issue No. 06 (J UNE) ISSN 2231-1009.
- [35] Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, L. L. (2008). SERVQUAL: A multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality. *Journal of Retailing*, 64(1), PP. 12-40.
- [36] Ranaweera, C., & Neely, A. (2003). Some moderating effects on the service quality-customer retention link. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 23, 230-248.
- [37] Rogers, M. s. (2003). *Diffusion of Innovations, 5th Edition* . New York: Free press.
- [38] Rose, S. (2000). *The truth about online banking*”, *money*, Vol. 29 No. 4, pp. 114-220.
- [39] Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2009). *Research methods for business students, 5th ed.* Harlow: Pearson Education.
- [40] Schindler, P. S., & Cooper, C. R. (2014). *Business research methods*. Boston: McGraw-Hill.
- [41] Sharma, M. (2006). Business Process Reengineering: A Tool to further Bank Strategic Goals. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 12(1), pp.65-74.
- [42] Shin, N., & Jemella, D. F. (2012). Business process reengineering and performance improvement: The case of Chase Manhattan Bank. *Business Process Management Journal*, 8(4), pp.351-363.
- [43] Stalk, M. (2010). Business Process Reengineering: A Tool to further Bank Strategic Goals. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, pp. 65-74.
- [44] Stevens, M. (2012). Getting the Process Right. *Marketing Business*.